

Household district	Study Number	Household Identification Number

CONSENT FORM

STUDY TITLE

2. The epidemiology of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella* at a household level in Malawi

Statement by adult participant:

Please circle Yes or No to confirm whether you agree or do not agree with each of the points below:

- I have read the information sheet or it has been read to me. Yes / No
- I have had the chance to ask questions and I am satisfied with the answers that I have been given. Yes / No
- I agree to take part but I know that I can change my mind at a later date. Yes / No
- I agree to supply a faecal sample at visits 1, 2 and 3 to be submitted as part of the study. Yes / No
- I understand that the second visit will take place one month following the first, and a third visit will take place six months after the first visit. Yes/No
- Yes/No
- I voluntarily agree to join the study. Yes/No
- I agree that should *E. coli* or non-typhoidal *Salmonella* be found in my sample that the sample may be shipped to the UK or Kenya to undergo whole genome sequencing.

Yes/No

Malawi-Liverpool-Wellcome
Clinical Research Programme

Name of household participant	Date	Signature	Signature
Impartial witness (if household owner has difficulty reading)	Date	Signature	Thumbprint
Staff obtaining consent	Date	Signature	Thumbprint

Research Nurse

Paediatric Research Ward

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TENTACLE

Consent Form v2.0

Date version effective 29th January 2019

